

The Pioneering Figure in the Search for “New Music” in 20th-Century Turkish Music: Yıldırım Gürses*

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Abstract

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Yıldırım Gürses developed a distinctive musical style beginning in the early 1960s by synthesizing the traditional elements of Turkish music with modern musical components. This study aims to evaluate Gürses's musical style in relation to the new musical movements that emerged globally in the twentieth century, through the concepts of modernization, massification, and synthesis. The musical idiom created by Gürses is examined within a holistic framework that positions him as a musical reformist who modernized tradition through reinterpretation. From the first quarter of the twentieth century onward, major transformations such as the rise of jazz, the movements of neoclassicism and expressionism, tendencies toward a return to folk music, and the emergence of electronic music led to the reinterpretation of traditional musical forms worldwide. In Turkey, this period coincided with the establishment of the Republic, during which the process of modernization, experienced on both institutional and aesthetic levels, was also reflected in the field of music. The Musical Reform (Musiki İnkılabı), which was implemented with revolutionary rhetoric, determination, and rigor by the Republican elites in the 1920s to transform culture, soon gave way to a reformist approach and, in later periods, to revision. From the early 1960s onward, Yıldırım Gürses occupied a central position in the transformation of Turkish music, creating an original understanding of a “new Turkish music” by combining the melodic and modal structure of Turkish music with the harmonic system of Western music, polyphonic orchestration, and elements of popular culture. This article comparatively evaluates Gürses's musical style alongside modernist and popular music movements referred to as “new music” on a global scale. The composer's inclination toward reconstructing tradition, his ability to popularize his music, and his synthesizing approach are examined in detail.

20. Yüzyıl Türk Müziğinde “Yeni Müzik” Arayışının Öncü İsmi: Yıldırım Gürses

Özet

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Yıldırım Gürses,
Yeni müzik
arayışları, Türk
müziğinde
modernleşme
ograns,
International
Education.

Yıldırım Gürses, 1960'lı yılların başlarından itibaren, Türk müziğinin geleneksel unsurlarını modern müzikal öğelerle sentezleyerek kendine özgü bir müzikal tarz geliştirmiştir. Bu çalışma, 20. yüzyılda dünyada ortaya çıkan “yeni müzik” akımlarıyla Yıldırım Gürses'in müzikal tarzını modernleşme, kitleleşme ve sentezlenme kavramları üzerinden ilişkilendirerek değerlendirmektedir. Gürses'i, yarattığı müzikal üslup ile geleneği yeniden yorumlayarak modernize eden bir müzik reformisti olarak değerlendiren bütüncül bir çerçevede sunmaktadır. Yirminci yüzyılın ilk çeyreğinden itibaren dünyada caz müziğinin yükselişi, neoklasizm, ekspresyonizm akımları, halk müziğine dönüş eğilimleri ve elektronik müziğin ortaya çıkışı gibi geniş kapsamlı dönüşümler, geleneksel müziklerin yeniden yorumlanmasına yol açmıştır. Türkiye'de Cumhuriyet'in kurulmasına denk gelen bu dönemde, hem kurumsal hem de estetik düzlemde yaşanan modernleşme süreci müzik alanına da yansımıştır. 1920'li yıllarda Cumhuriyet “elit”leri tarafından kültürün dönüştürülmesi için devrimci söylemlerle, kararlılık ve keskinlikle uygulamaya konulan “Musiki İnkılabı” kısa sürede yerini reformist bir anlayışa hatta daha sonraları revizyona bırakmış; Yıldırım Gürses de 1960'lı yılların başından itibaren Türk musikisindeki dönüşümün merkezinde yer alarak Türk müziğinin melodik ve makamsal yapısını Batı müziğinin armonik yapısı, çok sesli orkestrasyonu ve popüler kültür unsurlarıyla birleştirilerek özgün bir “yeni Türk müziği” anlayışı oluşturmuştur. Makalede Gürses'in müzikal tarzı dünyadaki “yeni müzik” olarak ifade edilen modernist ve popüler müzik hareketleriyle karşılaştırılarak değerlendirilmekte; bestecinin geleneği yeniden inşa etme yönelimi, müziğini kitleleştirme becerisiyle sentezci yaklaşımı irdelenmektedir.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Music is an expressive art that emerges as the outcome of the thoughts, emotions, perceptions, and observations of individuals who are born into and develop within the same cultural environment and share a common cultural ground. Although musical expression may appear to be an individual act, it cannot be considered independent of social life. Just as the twentieth century was an era of breakthroughs in science, technology, and social life, it also constituted a period of profound rupture in world music history, both culturally and stylistically. During this period, the art of music, rather than remaining content with the past, entered new quests through creative and experimental endeavors inspired by the aspiration to create the new.

In its general definition, “new music” refers to the severing of all ties with tonal music, which had been in use for approximately three hundred years (1600-1900), and to the turning of the pages of the post-tonal era in music history (Say, 2000, p. 468). The “new music” movement represents a rapidly developing process that strikingly reflects the intellectual and artistic transformation of the twentieth century, within which numerous movements emerged. In the first half of the twentieth century, four major orientations that adopted a comprehensive understanding encompassing multiple movements were inscribed into world music history under the general heading of “avant-garde music”:

1. Expressionism and Atonal Modernism: Developed by composers such as Arnold Schönberg, Alban Berg, and Anton Webern, expressionist aesthetics, also referred to as expressionism or outward expression, constitute a musical language aimed at externalizing the inner world and subjectivity, characterized by the dissolution of tonality and the prominence of psychological intensity (Say, 2000, p. 474).
2. Neoclassicism and the Return to Tradition: The twentieth century, while displaying vitality through its future-oriented tendencies, also brought to the fore a re-evaluation of the styles of past eras from a new perspective. Following the First World War, composers who did not wish to sever ties with tradition gave rise to a movement that reinterpreted the values of the past. Through the neoclassical movement he led, Igor Stravinsky (1882-1971) combined forms from earlier periods with modern harmonic and rhythmic elements, securing his place in history as one of the foremost composers of twentieth-century music, particularly through works such as *The Rite of Spring*¹ (Say, 2000, p. 483).
3. The Rise of Jazz and the Era of Popular Modernity: In the first half of the twentieth century, jazz emerged as a dynamic musical genre which, through improvisation, rhythmic freedom, and Afro-American aesthetic codes, became a symbol of both modernity and mass culture (Say, 2000, p. 490).
4. The Return to Folk Music: One of the great composers of the twentieth century, the Hungarian-born Béla Bartók, advocated that composers should draw upon folk music in a genuinely artistic sense, and that national colors rooted in folk traditions should be combined with modern compositional techniques (Say, 2000, p. 480).

Technological developments, which began in the late nineteenth century and accelerated particularly throughout the twentieth century, enabled musical products to reach wider audiences and establish new connections between composers and the masses. The rapid advancement of electronic and computer technologies, at a pace exceeding even the realm of imagination, allowed music to attain an unprecedented power of dissemination in history (Say, 2000, p. 507). All of these orientations that emerged in the first half of the twentieth century collectively constituted the movement referred to as “new music” by situating tradition within a new context. Due to changing socio-cultural dynamics, it is impossible for music to remain static throughout historical processes. New musical quests that crystallized particularly after the First World War progressed along three main axes: “modernization,” “massification,” and “synthesis.” While modernization advanced through the questioning of traditional elements and efforts to establish a new aesthetic style, music became part of mass culture through the widespread adoption of listening practices such as radio, records, and venues beyond the concert hall, thereby undergoing massification. At the same time, a synthetic musical structure emerged through the fusion of traditional music with folk music and modern Western techniques.

In Turkey, similar transformations occurred in the field of music following the proclamation of the Republic. Within the framework of Republican music policies, Western music institutions were established, folk music compilations were carried out, and new musical experiments were encouraged in line with the ideals of the “new

¹ The Rite of Spring (*Le sacre du printemps*) is Stravinsky’s first ballet composed in an atonal style.

state,” the “new nation,” and the “new music.” Music policies that progressed in parallel with Republican principles until the 1950s began to loosen with the acceleration of internal migration and the inevitable process of urbanization, and subsequently entered a “period of rupture” in the 1960s (Duygulu, 2024). The new lifestyle that society sought to adapt to from the 1950s onward, the alienation experienced by migrant populations undergoing profound cultural conflict, and the emergence of a new musical configuration shaped by the preferences of arabesque culture, which did not easily align with urban cultural traditions, rendered it necessary to reconsider and critically reassess music. Yıldırım Gürses², as a composer who emerged precisely within this context, defined his musical position through an artistic identity that both preserved the traditional *makam* structure of Turkish music and successfully appealed to popular music audiences. This article examines Yıldırım Gürses’s new musical style within the context of global “new music” movements and analyzes the composer’s approach to constructing a new musical language nourished by tradition through the concepts of modernization, massification, and synthesis.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Modernization

Modernization refers to the transition from patterns of thought and behavior shaped by principles and value systems rooted in tradition and determined by social and political processes, toward modes of thinking and acting aligned with elements considered appropriate to the modern age. In Europe, the process of modernization began with the intellectual and philosophical reactions that emerged during the Enlightenment, spanning roughly two centuries across the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, which challenged the dominance of the Church as the sole authority and advocated the liberation of reason and society. With the Industrial Revolution, these reactions gained economic momentum, accelerating the formation of a new model of the world.

In the context of music, modernization denotes the reinterpretation of tradition, the application of traditional elements through new Western techniques, processes of institutionalization, and aesthetic transformations. Stravinsky’s neoclassical works, Schoenberg’s atonal structures, and Bartók’s folk music-based approaches to modernism represent different manifestations of musical modernization. The “new music” movements that emerged globally in the twentieth century, such as neoclassicism, expressionism, the rise of jazz, folk music-based synthesis practices, and technological developments, converge around a shared principle: the radical reinterpretation of tradition.

While determining his musical position in the 1960s, Yıldırım Gürses adopted a similar stance, consistently striving to preserve his connection with tradition, yet frequently expressing in various statements his opposition to the presentation of tradition in a rigid, fossilized form³. Owing to the familial, religious, and social contexts into which he was born, Gürses was acculturated from an early age with all the elements of traditional Turkish music. Indicators such as the preservation of *makam* structure in his works, the use of the classical *şarkı* form, traditional *usul* patterns, and the conventional alignment between lyrics (*güfte*) and composition (*beste*) all attest to his commitment to “tradition” and to the importance he ascribed to “cultural continuity.” By offering a contemporary interpretation of tradition, the composer aimed, in a sense, to serve as a bridge between past and future. In the works examined, he did not depart from *makam* structure or song form, thus safeguarding tradition, while simultaneously employing the structural and technical features of Western music, behaving, in effect, as a modernist who presented tradition through a renewed interpretive framework.

2.2. Massification

Massification, which may be described as the process through which popular culture is embraced by broad segments of society, represents a form of adaptation unfolding over time as a mode of social change and transformation. In this process, also referred to as popularization, all cultural elements undergoing transformation are shaped in direct proportion to the tastes and pleasures of the masses. Whenever the cultural

² Yıldırım Gürses was born on January 21, 1938, in Bursa. Thanks to his father, Nasuhi Bey, who was known throughout Bursa for the beauty of his voice in religious music performances, he was brought up within Bursa’s “gezek” culture from his primary school years onward. Gürses, who completed middle school and high school in Bursa, carried out studies at the Bursa Turkish Music Society. During his high school years, with the encouragement of his teacher Faruk Üsküdarî, he received training in Turkish and Western music. He completed his higher education at the Ankara Academy of Economic and Commercial Sciences. In 1959, he took the entrance examination for the Ankara State Opera and became first in Turkey. In the same year, he received the “Interuniversity Voice King” award in a competition he entered. After working at the opera for seven to eight months, he left and in 1960 won first place once again in the examination opened by TRT Ankara Radio, continuing his work there. In 1962, he married Ayla, who, like himself, was a TRT vocal artist. From this marriage, his son Beyazıt Gürses was born in 1971. Throughout his life, he composed approximately 350 compositions, 60 of which were very well liked. Gürses, who has 49 compositions in the TRT repertoire, presented examples in various makams of traditional modal music. He generally composed his works in the *nihavend* and *muhayyerkürdi* makams. The artist passed away at the age of 62 as a result of a heart attack he suffered in Istanbul on November 18, 2000.

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vFoXEGGIQec&t=3400s>

policies pursued by those seeking to initiate change conflict with the preferences and enjoyment levels of large audiences, the masses may generate alternative elements, products, or patterns of behavior that more accurately reflect their own tastes. Numerous artistic, political, and religious movements throughout history have emerged as oppositional responses to dominant culture.

In the field of music, massification encompasses the processes by which musical production reaches large audiences, circulates widely through media, and becomes embedded in social consciousness. From the 1920s onward, jazz, blues, and other song genres became global phenomena through radio broadcasts and phonograph records (Gioia, 2011).

One of the principal objectives of music policies within the scope of Republican-era modernization movements was to disseminate the newly designed modern system to large audiences through a new cadre of cultural agents. From the 1930s onward, Republican cultural elites pursued music policies in coordination with the market and through planned initiatives, aiming to “massify” these policies and thereby convey Republican ideals to broader segments of society. As Duygulu (2024) characterizes it, the Republican era was an age of organization, marked by a positivist, Enlightenment-oriented structure rather than an Eastern, fatalistic, emotional, or nationalist one (p. 55). The earliest applications of this structure were evident in Western-oriented music education and in efforts to reform Turkish music by processing traditional musical forms through Western techniques. The ultimate goal was to adapt Western techniques to traditional music and to establish a system encompassing Western notation, compositional techniques, and instrumental methods. In practice, however, the musical massification of the Republic manifested as a model of “flexible synthesis,” wherein tradition became intertwined with market dynamics and criteria of modernization (Duygulu, 2024, p. 54). As a composer and performer of the period, Yıldırım Gürses likewise sought to position himself musically by adapting to the phenomenon of massification, which increasingly evolved toward populism.

2.3. Synthesis

Synthesis, which may be defined as the unification of diverse cultural and musical elements within a single aesthetic language, has been understood in Turkish modernization as the act of incorporating primarily technical elements from Western values and combining them with the country’s own cultural heritage. It is evident that both the Ottoman Empire and subsequent Turkish modernization movements have consistently been Western-referenced. From their inception, while the Ottomans preserved vital components such as language, religion, social behaviors, and moral values within their Eastern roots, they nevertheless chose to adopt administrative systems and technological knowledge from the West. Indeed, an examination of Turkish history reveals a society caught between Eastern roots and Western ideals. The strategies developed to adapt to these opposing value systems gradually evolved into a political stance, whereby balance was sought through the identification of a middle ground. This need for balance, which extended historically through to the Republican era, transformed in the early Republic into a comprehensive “policy of balance” applied across all domains, from politics and economics to education and culture (Duygulu, 2024, p. 39).

To ensure social cohesion, this consciously constructed and internalized balance policy needed to be pursued in music as in all other fields. A new society would inevitably require a new music. Contemporary Turkish society required a modern musical synthesis that remained connected to sounds transmitted through tradition while being shaped by Western technical features. The fundamental policy of the Republic aimed to unite society within a shared culture, and even a shared musical language, while simultaneously maintaining equilibrium with the West.

Yıldırım Gürses’s musical style likewise established its identity as an original eclectic approach by negotiating the tension between tradition and modernity, positioning itself at the intersection of Turkish music, popular music, and Western music. Bartók’s synthesis of folklore and modernism, Gershwin’s fusion of jazz and classical music, and the blending of local rhythms with Western harmony by Latin American composers similarly exemplify forms of synthesis within global “new music” movements (Say, 2000).

Within the scope of this article, these concepts provide appropriate analytical tools for understanding Yıldırım Gürses’s musical approach.

3. MODERNIZATION IN TURKISH MUSIC

The modernization of musical art in the early Republican period, which took “Western values” as its primary reference, was grounded in the internalization of Western orientalist musical discourse and in viewing

indigenous musical tradition through this lens⁴. The official musical discourse accompanying the *musiki inkılabı* (music reform) was shaped precisely under the influence of self-orientalism. Orientalism, operating hand in hand with Eurocentrism, renders the historical achievements of non-Western societies timeless and placeless, transforming them into museum artifacts incapable of being revitalized (Kanar, 2006, pp. 30-31). According to the Eurocentric view, all non-Western cultures will eventually dissolve into the “universal” cultural sphere of the West. Everything non-Western is perceived as representing the past of the West, which occupies the apex of historical development. The value of these cultures lies solely in the extent to which they have served as sources for Western progress. This orientalist conception of historical development also manifests itself in narratives of music history. Consequently, the “monophonic” music of the East, characterized as “primitive,” is assumed to have been superseded by the more “advanced” polyphonic music of the West and thereby relegated to history. This perspective is based on the assumption that all musics progress from simple to complex forms; other musical traditions are thus interpreted as pointing to the past of tonal Western music and gain value only insofar as they contribute to its development⁵.

From the mid-twentieth century onward, the political, social, and cultural transformations experienced in Turkey brought with them new stylistic and expressive quests in Turkish music. Within this process of “modernization,” the classical *makam* music tradition entered into interaction with Western harmony and polyphony, as well as with the broader accessibility and dissemination logic of popular music. In his own musical explorations, Yıldırım Gürses sought to preserve the traditional *makam* structure and the classical *şarkı* form, while at the same time adapting to the requirements of modernization by incorporating Western harmonic structures and polyphonic features into his works and embracing the mass dissemination characteristic of popular music. Within the scope of this article, these characteristics are exemplified through selected works by Yıldırım Gürses.

During the Republican period, Turkish music underwent not only structural and aesthetic transformations, but also institutional ones. Significant developments included the establishment of the *Musiki Muallim Mektebi* (School for Music Teachers) in 1924, the initiation of folk music compilation movements, the formation of radio institutions (Istanbul Radio in 1926 and Ankara Radio in 1938), the founding of the Ankara State Conservatory in 1936, and the widespread adoption of notation-based musical practices (Say, 2000).

3.1. The Restructuring of Traditional Turkish Music

By the mid-twentieth century, Turkish music was reshaped in both its traditional and popular dimensions. During this period, musical elements such as *makam* structure, *usul* conceptions, and the *şarkı* form were simplified in order to reach broader segments of the population (Behar, 1992). From the 1950s onward, the transition to a new economic system and the adoption of an American-style way of life loosened boundaries and social class distinctions within musical genres, giving rise to a dominant mass-oriented musical understanding. Although it may be argued that this period enabled forms of cultural permeability, one of the subdomains of popular culture, it should also be noted that economic and cultural polarizations became increasingly pronounced in musical terms. This environment provided fertile ground for composers such as Yıldırım Gürses to pursue new musical styles. The milieu in which Gürses was formed embodied a modernization aesthetic that did not reject tradition but sought to reshape it. The popularization of the *şarkı* form, shifts in market aesthetics, and the growing importance of orchestration are all characteristic features of this period.

3.2. A Periodization of Yıldırım Gürses’s Compositional Career

Within the scope of this article, the approximately thirty-year period spanning from Yıldırım Gürses’s first composition to the peak of his popularity has been evaluated in ten-year intervals, excluding what we designate as the “preparatory period.”

The preparatory period refers to the time in the late 1950s and early 1960s when the composer produced his first work, *İçime Hep Hüzün Doluyor* (“My Heart Is Always Filled with Sadness”), a phase in which tendencies toward popularization had not yet become clearly visible. *İçime Hep Hüzün Doluyor* represents Yıldırım Gürses’s first composition. Following this work, the artist gradually entered a trajectory of increasing popularization (see Figure 1).

⁴ According to E. Said, Orientalism is the doctrine of the West’s dominance over and sovereignty over the East. Although Orientalism is detached from the East, the real East is in fact a source of inspiration for the West. The West has created a fictional East that is unrelated to reality. This situation has led to a crisis of identity in non-Western cultures. (Edward Said, *Orientalism, Western Conceptions of the Orient*, trans. Berna Yıldırım, Metis Publications, Istanbul, 2017)

⁵ This Eurocentric view related to music has influenced even thinkers such as Adorno and Thomas Mann, who put forward pessimistic views regarding the current state of Western music. (For detailed information on the subject, see Edward Said, *Musical Elaborations*.)

Usulü : Curcuna
Yayın No : 658

RAST ŞARKI
(İçime Hep Hüzün Doluyor)

Güfte : Yıldırım Gürses
Beste : Yıldırım Gürses

Figure 1.

This period, which corresponds to the late 1950s and is referred to here as the “Preparatory Period,” may be characterized as a phase in which Gürses, in a sense, sought to establish a bridge between tradition and modernity. While the composer endeavored to remain faithful to the formal conventions of classical Turkish music, he simultaneously adopted a cautious openness toward Western music (see Figure 2).

Figure 2.

Although the work gives the impression of having been composed in the *Rast makam*, in the *curcuna usul*, and in the *şarkı* form, thus conforming to the traditional frameworks of Turkish music- the use of syllabic meter (*hece ölçüsü*), the employment of a highly plain and everyday language in the lyrics, and the presence of a fluent and memorable rhythmic-melodic structure reveal the influence of popular music. Moreover, the work’s structure, which aligns with the G majör-D major scales, its notational system, and its dramatic rises and falls clearly demonstrate the impact of Western music. The piece consists of 36 measures and unfolds in the form of “Zemin-Nakarar-Meyan-Nakarar.” At the same time, through its melismatic texture, *usul*, and modulations (*geçkiler*), the work also displays a strong adherence to traditional form (see Figure 3).

Figure 3.

The 1960s represent the years in which Yıldırım Gürses began his professional musical career and gradually gained nationwide recognition through competitions. Music and vocal competitions were among the rising cultural phenomena of the 1960s, and the “Golden Microphone” (*Altın Mikrofon*) competition, which left a decisive mark on this decade, undoubtedly played a major role in Gürses’s career. With his first-place award for the song *Gençliğe Veda* (“Farewell to Youth”), the artist began to ascend the steps of fame.

Gençliğe Veda occupies a lasting place among the memorable compositions of the 1960s as an eclectic work that combines the modal characteristics of traditional music, the intense emotional emphases of popular music, and the harmonic and dramatic elements of Western music within Yıldırım Gürses’s compositional career. The 1960s, which we designate as the “First Period” of his compositional output, are marked by a style that is faithful to *makam* principles, dignified, disciplined, and refined, while also being the years in which the structural and technical features of Western music became firmly integrated into his musical language (see Figure 4).

Figure 4.

Although this work was composed in the *muhayyer kürdî makam* of traditional Turkish music, in the *sofyan usul*, and in the *şarkı* form, its notational language employs exclusively Western musical terminology (e.g., *pizzicato*, *ritardando*). Moreover, the piece departs from the melismatic (*melismatique*) texture characteristic of traditional music and instead adopts a syllabic (*syllabique*) structure (see Examples 4-5).

Figure 5.

Despite its lyrical narrative and simplified structure, the work has become one of the prominent examples of popular music due to its memorable, repetition-based lyrics and its melodic structure that readily lends itself to accompaniment. The individual sorrow expressed in the piece, the sense of fatalism articulated in the lyrics (e.g., “my departed youth will never return”), and the dramatic repetitions bear clear similarities to the emotional excesses characteristic of arabesque music (see Figure 6).

Figure 6.

Western musical techniques are also evident in terms of composition, notation, harmonic coherence, and dramatic effect. In the *recitative*⁶ section between measures 49 and 59, a remarkable correspondence is achieved between the semantic content of the lyrics and the melodic line; through melodic softening and sudden outcries, expressive contrasts are conveyed with great skill within a few passages (see Figure 7).

Figure 7.

Between measures 69 and 76, the repeated iteration of the words “*elveda*” (“farewell”) serves to extend the conclusion of the work in a dramatic manner, leaving a powerful musical impression on the listener (see Figure 8).

⁶ The recitative technique is a singing technique taken from the opera/romance tradition of Western music. In this technique, the rhythm becomes freer, and the lyrics proceed in a speech-like manner accompanied by music.

Figure 8.

The 1970s, described as a period of estrangement or “disillusionment” for Yıldırım Gürses in relation to the press and official institutions, may nonetheless be regarded as one of the most productive phases of his compositional career. *Son Mektup* (“The Last Letter”) and *Bir Garip Yolcuyum* (“I Am a Strange Traveler”) stand out as the defining works of what we designate as the “Second Period” of the composer’s creative output.

“*Son Mektup*” constitutes a compelling example representing the intense popularization experienced in Turkish music, particularly from the 1960s onward and the consequent search for new expressive approaches. Within a single work, efforts to integrate traditional *makam* music with Western harmony, experiments in polyphonizing Turkish music, and the emotional emphasis characteristic of arabesque music are brought together. In the orchestral arrangement, the prominence of string instruments is evident through extended accompaniments, while the *kanun* and *ud* enrich the melodic texture. The piano and rhythm instruments, on the other hand, form the foundation of Western harmony. From this, it becomes clear that Yıldırım Gürses’s conception of “polyphonic light Turkish art music” (*çok sesli hafif Türk sanat müziği*) is grounded in the effort to present traditional *makam* music to listeners through Western techniques and with the accompaniment of a large instrumental ensemble. This effort reflects the new quests of Turkish music under conditions of intense popularization (see Figure 9).

Usulü : NİHAVENT ŞARKI (Son Mektup) Güfte : Yıldırım Gürses
 Yayın No : 660 Beste : Yıldırım Gürses

Figure 9.

In this work, which is in the classical *şarkı* form, the structure consists of: Introduction (performed by a large instrumental ensemble and evoking the character of a *taksim*) + *Zemin* + *Nakarat* + Chorus. The Western song form (A-B-A’) entered Turkish music following Republican-era music reforms. In measures 1-12, the introduction features a *kanun*-led progression that evokes the *taksim* style and articulates the scale of the *makam*. The melodic motifs, constructed through ascending and descending yet stepwise motion, conform to the “melismatic” structure of classical Turkish music, with no intervallic leaps observed, constituting, in a sense,

a reference to the classical *meşk* tradition. In measures 13 and 14, a transition to a Western-style “lively and rhythmic” tempo creates an emotional shift and prepares the listener for the instrumental interlude (*aranağme*) (see Figure 9).

Figure 10.

From these measures onward, intervallic leaps begin to appear. Between measures 15 and 27, the lively and rhythmic instrumental interlude of the song unfolds. In this section, the pitch intervals expand, leap-based melodic motion characteristic of Western music becomes dominant, and the vocal line gains greater prominence. While the melody is supported by tonal cadences compatible with Western harmony, brief *Hicaz* modulations (*geçkiler*) in measures 20 and 21 heighten the emotional emphasis (see Figure 10). The same modulations reappear in measures 44 and 45, coloring the melody and preventing monotony. By incorporating the beloved *Hicaz* sonorities of traditional Turkish music into a modern harmonic framework, the work simultaneously alludes to classical tradition and models a new modern stylistic search (see Figure 10).

Between measures 28 and 58 lies the lyrical (*güfte*) section of the work, designated by the term *strofa*. The melodic phrases are short, clear, and structured to be sung in a single breath, each lasting four measures. At phrase endings, sustained half notes are employed. This lyrical section immediately draws attention through its syllabic (*syllabique*) structure, in contrast to the melismatic (*melismatique*) texture of traditional *makam* music. Throughout the entire work, the syllabic technique, where each syllable corresponds to a single note, as in “an-la-ar-tık / an-la-be-ni / u-nut-bü-tün / ge-çen-le-ri”, is consistently maintained (see Figure 11).

Figure 11.

The use of double stops in the refrain (*nakarât*) section between measures 37 and 52 represents a distinctive feature demonstrating the composer’s experiments with polyphonizing Turkish music. Here, a deliberate effort is observed to skillfully merge Western harmony with modal compatibility. In this Western-style two-voice texture, the upper voice functions as the melodic driver, while the lower voice provides harmonic support moving in parallel. These double stops may be interpreted as Gürses’s attempt to symbolically integrate Western harmony without undermining the classical monophonic structure, thus preserving his ties to tradition. For Turkish music, whose general character is monophonic, this practice constitutes an unconventional approach and serves as an indicator of new stylistic explorations (see Figure 12).

Figure 12.

“Bir Garip Yolcuym,” by contrast, maintains its connection to the traditional *şarkı* form of classical music while striving to attain the universality of Western music through its instrumental ensemble, particularly the arrangement of string instruments, and its harmonic cadences. By elegantly combining themes such as loneliness, estrangement, fate, and sacrifice drawn from arabesque music with the inner voice of the people, the work embodies a structure closely aligned with the spirit of its time (see Figure 13).

MUHAYYERKÜRDİ ŞARKI

BİR GARİP YOLCUYUM HAYAT YOLUNDA

USÛLÜ : SOFYAN GÜFTE ve BESTE Yıldırım GÜRSES

Figure 13.

Composed in the *muhayyer kürdî makam*, which is easily harmonized and readily performed with Western instruments due to its proximity to Western minor scales, and in the *sofyan* (4/4) *usul*, the work adheres to the classical *şarkı* form. While *Bir Garip Yolcuym* exhibits a stylistically more restrained character compared to the arabesque songs of its period, it may nonetheless be said to fall under the influence of arabesque music in terms of both its melodic structure and its lyrics: “*Bir garip yolcuym hayat yolunda, yolunu kaybetmiş perişanım ben...*” (“I am a strange traveler on the road of life, lost and miserable...”). These lyrics are directly connected to the themes of fatalism, spiritual collapse, introversion, and loneliness that lie at the core of arabesque music. Words such as “*yalan dünya*” (false world), “*garip*” (strange), “*perişan*” (miserable), and “*kurbanyım*” (I am your sacrifice), used throughout the song, appear as expressions of a melancholic state marked by self-pity and lamentation. Gürses, however, articulates these sentiments not through coarse

expression but through a poetic tone and aesthetic language, thereby distancing himself from the harshness often associated with arabesque style.

Furthermore, the frequent use of leap-based intervals (perfect fifths, fourths, and thirds), which are relatively uncommon in traditional Turkish *makam* music, particularly in the instrumental interlude, as well as the fragmented, repetition-based melodic structure observed throughout the piece, shift the work away from a strictly traditional character toward a more free-form style. Additionally, the cadence does not conform to traditional *makam* principles, further indicating the presence of diverse musical interactions. In Turkish music, regardless of the melodic progression (*seyir*), works traditionally resolve on the *durak* pitch, the first degree of the scale (see Figure 14).

Figure 14.

The third period of the periodization proposed for Yıldırım Gürses's professional musical career may be regarded as the most brilliant phase of his artistic life; at the same time, it also coincides with significant terminological developments in the history of Turkish music.

From the very beginning of his compositional career, Yıldırım Gürses consistently emphasized that Turkish art music should be examined in two distinct categories: Classical Turkish Art Music (*Klasik Türk Sanat Müziği*) and Light Turkish Art Music (*Hafif Türk Sanat Müziği*). According to Gürses, classical music must be performed in the most authentic manner possible and should remain faithful to its original form. In the early 1980s, supported and encouraged by the TRT institution, a new musical style emerged based on this conceptual framework articulated by Gürses: "Polyphonic Light Turkish Music" (*Çok Sesli Hafif Türk Müziği*). With the institutional backing of TRT, Gürses shaped this new style in accordance with the aesthetic criteria of official culture, while simultaneously functioning as an artist who gave voice to the internalized emotions of the public.

The song *Affetmem Asla Seni* ("I Will Never Forgive You") appears to articulate the collective psychological state generated by Turkey's political climate in the early 1980s. With lyrics by Mustafa Sevilen and composed by Yıldırım Gürses in the *nihavend makam* and *düyek* (8/8) *usul*, the song evokes the prohibitions, restrictions, silence, economic hardship, and inward withdrawal that followed the military coup of 12 September 1980. Although the lyrics may initially appear to express romantic disappointment toward a beloved, "*Ateş olup yaksan da / Gonca güller taksan da / Ahu olup baksan da / Affetmem asla seni...*" ("Even if you burn like fire, even if you adorn yourself with rosebuds, even if you gaze like a gazelle, I will never forgive you"), they can also be interpreted as a muted and implicit protest reflecting the suppressed emotions of the period. The widespread sense of "unforgiveness" within society is transformed into an internalized rebellion, subtly concealed through Gürses's civilized worldview and melodically romantic aesthetic.

Affetmem Asla Seni is structured in the classical *şarkı* form, with each section composed as a stanza: *Zemin + Meyan + Nakarat* (A-B-C). Following an eight-measure instrumental interlude (*aranağme*), the *zemin* section introduces the *makam*, the *meyan* section reaches melodic and emotional climax through various modulations (*geçkiler*), and the *nakarat* concludes the piece with resolute expressions by returning to the principal scale of the *makam*. While the *aranağme* features a melismatic (*melismatique*) texture, the vocal sections entirely adopt a syllabic (*syllabique*) structure (see Figure 15).

Usulü : Düyek
Yayın No : 673

NİHAVENT ŞARKI
(Affetmem Asla Seni)

Güfte : Mustafa Sevilen
Beste : Yıldırım Gürses

Figure 15.

Throughout the vocal sections of the piece, the syllabic technique is consistently employed. Western music's intervallic leaps and harmonic language come into play within the vocal passages, and the compositional technique skillfully translates semantic meaning into musical gesture. In the phrase "*Ateş olup yaksan da / Gonca güller taksan da / Ahu olup baksan da...*," the melody begins on the *durak* pitch and gradually ascends into higher registers, metaphorically evoking the intensification of fire. In contrast, the descending melodic motion from high to low in "*Affetmem asla seni*," culminating in a sudden resolution on the *nevâ*, the dominant pitch (*güçlü*) of the *makam*, expresses decisiveness and resolve (see Figure 16).

Figure 16.

The melody corresponding to the lines "*Som altından taç olsan / Aşkına muhtaç olsan / Derdime ilaç olsan*," articulated almost as a cry in the upper register, emphasizes pride and emotional intensity (see Figure 17).

Figure 17.

Although the work conforms to the TRT format of the period, it exhibits a distinctly theatrical character. Within the traditional *makam-usul* framework of Turkish music, it incorporates Western harmonic practices, orchestral arrangements, and the emotive expressiveness of popular music. The stylistic approach Gürses had been developing since the mid-1960s is clearly evident in this composition. The piano and string ensemble provide harmonic support, generating Western-style cadences while remaining faithful to the *makam*, thereby imparting a "modern" auditory quality to the work. Without departing from the classical *makam-usul* structure, the piece symbolically synthesizes Western harmony and arabesque emotionality, representing a multifaceted stylistic exploration. With *Affetmem Asla Seni*, Yıldırım Gürses successfully combined elements of three musical genres in a refined and aesthetically coherent manner, enabling the work to reach a broad audience.

The 1980s may be described as the “maturity period” of Yıldırım Gürses’s musical style, a decade in which he reached both material and spiritual culmination. During this era, marked by the advancement of studio technology in Turkey and the establishment of Gürses’s own recording studio in 1984, musical arrangements increasingly assumed the character of “mini symphonies.” Large orchestral formations, film music style string writing, the integration of harmony and *makam*, piano parts within the orchestral texture, dramatic vocal delivery, and the aesthetics of popular music became defining features of the period.

3.3. The Modern Interpretation of Traditional *Makam* Structure in Gürses’s Works

As observed in Yıldırım Gürses’s compositions, the composer preserves the *makam* and *seyir* characteristics of traditional Turkish music while simplifying the melodic material and restructuring it within a modern song form. This approach reflects an attitude of “reconstruction” comparable to Stravinsky’s modernization of classical forms. In Gürses’s songs, the modal features of traditional Turkish music are retained, yet simultaneously reshaped within a modern, scaled song format. Such an approach closely aligns with the neoclassical tendency within global “new music” movements. In this respect, Gürses shares a parallel conceptual framework with composers such as Stravinsky, Bartók, and Gershwin.

3.4. Harmony, Polyphony, and Orchestration in Yıldırım Gürses’s Compositions

Although Yıldırım Gürses’s approach to polyphony reflects a positive orientation rooted in his modernist identity, it also entails significant technical challenges. The question of whether to employ Western harmonic principles or the older contrapuntal tradition has remained a persistent point of debate. If polyphony is understood as the simultaneous perception of multiple independent voice layers, such polyphonic stratification is rarely encountered in Gürses’s music. Instead, the use of a large orchestral ensemble to enhance musical volume and texture emerges as a more practical strategy. In this sense, polyphony in Gürses’s music manifests primarily through orchestral density.

One of the defining characteristics of Gürses’s musical identity is “multi-instrumentation” (*çok sazlılık*). Gürses articulated this perspective explicitly in an interview with Murat Meriç for the TRT program *Bir Varmış Bir Yokmuş*, broadcast shortly before his death in 2000:

“I first encountered Western music through *Carmen*. Later, I began taking notation and harmony lessons from Mithat Fenmen. At that time, I recognized the perspective and depth of Western music. I knew the place of the East, and I knew my own place. I engaged in religious music and also learned classical music very well. I realized then that Western music was a science, and I was filled with the desire and love to learn it. From that point on, changes began to appear in my songs. My knowledge of Western music, harmony, and vocal technique created a distinction between myself and my fellow composers and performers. Even at that time, I began searching for polyphony. However, we know that the Western polyphonic system does not encompass the sounds of our music. It is not possible to play *segâh*, *hüzzam*, or *uşşak*, that is, certain pitches unique to Turkish music, on the piano. Therefore, a search within the harmonic system was necessary. We began composing music in forms compatible with polyphony, based on what we could learn within our own capacities. This broke the taboos of our classical formation. Yet we ultimately proved inadequate, because the classical harmonic system does not contain the sounds of Turkish music. I truly wish to admit this. We sought polyphony, but we did not find it. What we achieved was multi-instrumentation. Still, we approached a form suitable for polyphony. Outside our classical music tradition, we began performing what we call light Turkish music, much like arranging the garden of a temple” (Meriç, 2022, p. 77).

In the orchestras that perform Gürses’s works, the most striking feature is the dominance of string instruments. This emphasis on strings, also prominent in the arabesque music of the period, undoubtedly serves to increase the perceived musical volume and intensity. Rather than employing full Western harmony, Gürses’s compositions rely on limited cadential patterns and parallel chordal textures intended to add harmonic color. This approach bears resemblance to the popular harmonic practices of composers such as Milhaud and Gershwin. Without abandoning the monodic structure of Turkish music, Gürses utilizes light harmonization, effective cadential structures derived from Western tonality, and accompaniment textures with polyphonic connotations. These practices parallel the hybrid harmonic experiments characteristic of twentieth-century “new music” movements, such as the jazz-influenced harmonies of *Les Six*⁷, the transparency associated with Ravel⁸,

⁷ A French modernist group led by composers such as Darius Milhaud, Francis Poulenc, and Arthur Honegger, whose aim was to create a light, neoclassical, and jazz-influenced French style that had freed itself from the influence of Wagner. See: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Les-Six>

and Milhaud's polytonality. Gürses's modernization is not radical; rather, it represents a conciliatory form of modernization.

3.5. Vocal Style and Emotional Aesthetics

In terms of vocal delivery, Gürses's use of *vibrato* in song performance, elongated phrase structures at the end of measures, *melismatique* ornamentation, dramatic expressive style, and clear articulation may be interpreted as an adaptation of expressionist intensity to the idiom of popular music. Although his style evokes arabesque music, his distinctive interpretative approach situates him closer to a form of romantic classicism.

Acting with a mission of modernization without severing ties with tradition, or of building a bridge between tradition and modernity, Yıldırım Gürses also reflects arabesque emotionality in his song lyrics, where the affective states of the public are treated with subtlety and refinement. Social developments experienced between 1960 and 1990, particularly the phenomena of migration and the resulting feelings of loneliness and identity crisis, are articulated in Gürses's lyrics with emotional depth yet within an aesthetically refined framework. This process, which also contains a form of expression of the political conjuncture that shifted roughly every decade, corresponds to the years in which Gürses emerged as a symbol of a new interpretative understanding in Turkish music performance. This emotional discourse, foregrounding individual emotions and inner conflicts, may be regarded as parallel to the psychic intensity of expressionism's outward emotional projection. Gürses, however, articulates this intensity by integrating it with aesthetic restraint rather than excessive dramatization. This stylistic orientation is also consistent with Stokes's (2020) concept of "urban music culture," which further accounts for Gürses's distinctive artistic position.

3.6. Gürses in the Context of Modernization

Gürses is an artist who does not reproduce traditional Turkish *makam* music as a fixed and static form; rather, he reconstructs it through modern musical elements. He simplifies *seyir*, adapts *makam* modulations (*geçkiler*) to what may be termed the "popular ear," and creates a sense of modern fluidity by placing melody at the center of musical expression. These characteristics correspond to the dimension of modernization understood as the "creative transformation of tradition."

3.7. Gürses in the Context of Massification

In his search for new musical expressions, Gürses extensively employed emerging technical features that few before him had dared to use, thereby seeking to capture the spirit of his time. In the twentieth century, music was disseminated to the masses through radio and records, and Gürses's songs similarly reached wide audiences via radio broadcasts. From the 1960s onward, TRT radio stations became the most significant instruments enabling the massification of Turkish music. The successful circulation of Gürses's songs is closely related to his position as a composer shaped by the radio era. The rise of jazz, tango, and popular songs are all products of massification, and it is precisely at this point that the concept of massification converges with modernization.

The highly fluid melodic structures of Gürses's works in terms of rhythm and vocal articulation, the use of clear Turkish expressed through everyday language that listeners can easily pronounce and remember, and the integration of these features with romantic sensibility undoubtedly constitute key literary and expressive elements that facilitated the mass dissemination of his music.

Gürses's works are positioned differently from the rebellious and coarse expressiveness of provincial arabesque music, instead representing a musical design of urban modern sensibility. The emotional expression in his compositions avoids the crushing, lamenting, and insurgent tone of arabesque music, and is instead conveyed through a dignified, civilized perspective and a refined emotional aesthetic characteristic of Gürses. In this respect, his work bears similarities to the modes of massification observed in jazz, blues, and the chanson tradition within global popular music cultures. From the early 1960s onward, Yıldırım Gürses occupied a central position in the transformation of Turkish music, functioning as a revisionist figure who shifted Turkish music away from being the preserve of an elite audience toward becoming the "modern music" of the broader public.

3.8. Gürses in the Context of Synthesis

One of the fundamental tendencies of global "new music" movements is synthesis. Bartók synthesized folk music with modern harmonic structures; Stravinsky combined older forms with modern rhythms; Gershwin

⁸ **Maurice Ravel (1875-1937)**: French composer and pianist. He is one of the most important composers of the twentieth century, especially in the field of orchestration. He described his music not as "revolutionary" but as "evolutionary." His music is inclined less toward Impressionism and more toward a somewhat expressive, even traditional, musical approach (Say, 2000, p. 460).

merged jazz and classical music; and in Latin America, local folk traditions were integrated with Western techniques. Gürses's works likewise constitute a synthesis of three dimensions. Traditional *makam* music is combined with the harmonic color and tonal influence of Western music, as well as with the song form and emotional discourse of popular music, thereby exemplifying synthesis in its fullest sense. This configuration directly corresponds to the hybrid musical structures observed within global "new music" movements.

The musical synthesis Gürses established within the triangle of *makam* music, modernity, and popularity opened a new aesthetic domain in Turkey and rendered the composer unique. This represents a clear example of cultural permeability, or, in other terms, hybridization.

Although Gürses intersects with arabesque music in emotional themes such as melancholy, broad vibrato, and internalized dramatic expression, he does not transgress the aesthetic boundary he establishes between himself and arabesque music, drawing instead upon the dignified posture and refined discipline of traditional Turkish music. In this way, he produces a refined synthesis without disrupting *makam seyir*, achieving a balanced and sophisticated musical integration.

4. CONCLUSION

The social, political, and cultural transformations that have taken place in Turkey since the second half of the twentieth century have provided fertile ground for new artistic explorations in Turkish music. The disintegration observed in the performance and transmission of the structural characteristics of traditional music accelerated particularly during the 1960s. Alongside the increasing efforts toward popularization and massification under the influence of popular culture, the classical *makam* music tradition entered into interaction with the harmonic structures and polyphony of Western music, as well as with the intense emotional expressiveness of popular music. In song lyrics, a growing emphasis on individual themes drawn from everyday life and on easily comprehensible expressions associated with consumer society can be observed, while Western harmonic structures are increasingly employed at the technical level.

As a composer raised within traditional culture yet exposed to diverse cultural influences, Yıldırım Gürses placed Turkish music in a comparative relationship with Western music. In establishing this relationship, he brought traditional *makam*, *usul*, and formal structures into contact with Western harmony, polyphonic orchestration, Western-style dramatic expression, and popular song forms. At the core of Gürses's conception of "polyphonic light Turkish art music" (*çok sesli hafif Türk sanat müziği*) lies the effort to present traditional *makam* music to audiences through Western techniques and the accompaniment of a large instrumental ensemble. This endeavor embodies the new searches undertaken by Turkish music under conditions of intense popularization.

Yıldırım Gürses produced a synthesis in Turkish music that both preserves tradition and facilitates modernization. The musical character of his works parallels the new music tendencies observed in twentieth-century world music. The concepts of modernization, massification, and synthesis provide a robust framework for understanding both the historical and aesthetic dimensions of Gürses's music. His oeuvre represents the distinctive voice of a period in which traditional *makam* culture in Turkey gained renewed meaning in a modern era, and in which a new shared space emerged between the public and art music.

Despite his profound mastery of the traditional *makam* music system, Gürses adopted an approach that sought innovation through transformation rather than abandonment of classical forms. This approach simultaneously ensured "cultural continuity" while allowing for "intercultural permeability," positioning Gürses within a modernist and revisionist paradigm. The harmonic textures, the prominence of string instruments, the use of piano and guitar accompaniment, and the integration of Western technical elements into modal music in his works all reflect efforts to reconcile Western musical practices with *makam*-based traditions. Although it is not possible to speak of a fully developed Western harmonic system in Gürses's music, his compositions nonetheless convey a sense of rich texture and expanded musical volume, subtly acclimating listeners unfamiliar with polyphonic music to such sonorities. Gürses's translation of the *makam* tradition into a contemporary musical language bears structural resemblance to Stravinsky's modernization of Baroque and Classical forms. In this sense, Gürses reconstructed the melodic logic of traditional Turkish music through the rhythmic, harmonic, and formal codes of twentieth-century popular music. This reconfiguration of tradition through modern interpretation demonstrates clear parallels with the neoclassical orientation of "new music" movements.

Operating with a mission of modernization without severing ties with tradition, or of building a bridge between tradition and modernity, Gürses also incorporated arabesque emotionality into his song lyrics, wherein the affective states of the public are treated with sensitivity and refinement. Social events between 1960 and 1990,

particularly the phenomena of migration and the resulting experiences of loneliness and identity crisis, are articulated in Gürses's lyrics with emotional depth yet within an aesthetically elegant framework. This process, which also functions as a form of expression of shifting political conjunctures roughly every decade, encompasses the years in which Gürses became emblematic of a new interpretative understanding in Turkish music performance. The emotional inward discourse present in his works further aligns with expressionist aesthetics, also referred to as expressivism, characterized by the outward projection of the inner world, the dissolution of tonality, and heightened psychological intensity.

The use of clear, everyday Turkish that can be easily articulated and understood by a broad audience, combined with a romantic sensibility, constitutes one of the key factors contributing to the popularization of Gürses's works. Such accessible lyrical constructions appear frequently in his compositions, positioning Gürses as a composer intent on being understood. This orientation toward reaching and engaging the public indicates that Gürses adopted a determined stance toward massification from the earliest stages of his career. In his musical explorations, he extensively employed emerging technical features that few before him had dared to utilize, striving to capture the spirit of his era. Just as jazz spread to mass audiences through radio and recordings, Gürses's music similarly reached wide publics through media channels. His model of massification thus parallels the trajectories observed in jazz and blues.

Another notable parallel can be drawn with folkloric modernism. Just as Bartók processed folk music material through modern techniques, Gürses reconfigured *makam* music within a modern popular framework.

Ultimately, Yıldırım Gürses's musical style constitutes a modern, urban conception of new Turkish music, developed along the axes of modernization (reconstructing tradition and adapting it to contemporary forms), massification (creating an aesthetic capable of reaching broad audiences), and synthesis (the integration of Turkish music, Western music, and popular culture). Core tendencies of global new music movements, such as redefining tradition, combining folk elements with modern forms, hybridizing musical language, and engaging with mass culture, are strongly evident in Gürses's musical production. For this reason, Yıldırım Gürses should be regarded not merely as a composer of romantic songs, but also as one of the distinctive representatives of twentieth-century music modernization in Turkey.

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<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vFoXEGGIQec&t=3400s> Arabesque Roundtable Discussion.